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Globalization and State Sovereignty

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Abstract

Globalization unarguably has many advantages, but the disadvantages far outweigh the advantages. The hopes in the early 1990s that growing international economic interdependence would provide the basis for a peaceful world order have not come to fruition. Worst of all, globalization leads to the diminution of states' sovereignty thereby exposing weaker nations to the vagaries of economic manipulations of international financial institutions like the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank and the World Trade Organization. These organizations which are agents of globalization, founded and controlled by the highly industrialized nations have not the survival of the weaker nations at heart. Consequently, weak economic nations are put to the worst in the world system due to the high cost of economic globalization. This paper recommends that weak economies should first build strong economic base for their countries before opening up their economies to the international market economy if they are going to survive the global holocaust.

Introduction

Up till now, states in the international system hold their sovereignty sacrosanct. None wants to share. However, the benefits of international intercourse are so enormous that no state can afford to exist in isolationism without interacting with other nations. States that previously held the policy of isolationism have rescinded it in the 21st Century.

Regrettably, as states interact with other states, they inadvertently limit their sovereignty by acquiescing to the conditions for membership in some international organizations which are agents of globalization because

of the benefits which they stand to gain from membership in these organizations. By also signing or accepting the conditions attached to treaties, alliances and other compacts they enter in with other entities in the international system, states limit their sovereignty. An example of such compacts is the Kyoto Protocol under which signatories agree to cap specific emissions in an attempt to stem the threat of global climate change (Haass, 2006:2).

Some scholars agree to this view of voluntary diminution of sovereignty by states. These scholars believe that globalization contributes to the change and reduction of nomenclature and scope of state sovereign powers and besides it is a bilateral process. On the one hand, the factors are strengthening that fairly undermines the countries' sovereignty, and on the other hand, most states voluntarily and deliberately limit the scope of their sovereignty.

And not surprisingly, the exigencies of present day international relations demands increasingly more of such interactions and this also means that states continue and would continue to lose their sovereignty. In recent times, one frequently hears statements like, "the world is fast becoming a global village". In other words, the international system is gradually moving towards globalization.

Long before the creation of the term, "globalization" transnational activities that impinge upon the exclusiveness of national territories have been on going. This means in effect that states have never ever exercised total political or economic regulatory monopoly over their territories at any point in time. The increase in global business mergers to form mega corporations and the globalization of communications especially the introduction of the World Wide Web has affected state autonomy and sovereignty.

Operational Definitions:

Globalization concerns the developments of the state and market economy. It entails the quantity, speed and significance of transnational flow of personnel, machinery, technology, ideas, goods, services, money, drugs, viruses, emails, weapons, etc across national boundaries (Haass, 2006:2). It has to do with global integration or the rise of a world market,

world economy or world society wider in scope and coverage than some empires in the past. The dimensions of globalization include "the rise of transnational organizations, the unprecedented worldwide expansion of corporations and market economies, global capacities of military superpowers, the ability of technology to limit spatial barriers, the consolidation of an international legal system", and more (Waisbord *et al*).

Globalization is the process of integrating regional economies, societies, and cultures through communication, transportation, and trade. Economic integration refers to the integration of national economies into the international economy through trade, foreign direct investment, capital flows, migration, the spread of technology, and military presence. In other words, globalization in an economic context refers to the reduction and removal of barriers between national borders in order to facilitate the flow of goods, capital, services and labour.

However, globalization is usually recognized as being driven by a combination of economic, technological, socio-cultural, political, and biological factors. The term can also refer to the transnational circulation of ideas, languages, or popular culture through acculturation.

Globalization captures the novelty of emergent conditions in the international system. Nor is the term completely new. The term was first used in 1897 by Charles Taze Russel, the founder of the Bible Student Movement when he coined the term 'corporate giants'. It became popularized by economists and other social scientists in the 1960s (Wikipedia). Since then the term has come to replace the word, "internationalization" which was hitherto used. Amplified by business media usage, the term has become the most popular word in the 1990s. Today, it is used to represent all shades of things that has global appeal, from taste of food to clothing, "...music, sports and entertainment, provision of financial services and the directions of scientific research" (Weiss, 1997:2).

In spite of this however, globalization is essentially an economic process. It involves "ongoing transformations of world capitalism and state sovereignty" (Arrighi 1997:1). Some critics see globalization as "an ideological category that hides the continuities of today's global economy

with older forms of imperialism..." (Jessop, 2003:17). Therefore some writers have condemned it as modern imperialism.

Nonetheless, globalization focuses on the extent to which the world economy is becoming more interconnected in a way that events in one part of the world can come to have significant consequences for individuals and communities in other distant parts of the world.

Politically, globalization has led to the intervention of powerful states in the political or social process of other nations in the cloak of humanitarian considerations. Richard N. Haass cited America's intervention in Afghanistan's by removing the Taliban government, which was believed to have provided access and support to al-Qaeda and America's preventive war against Iraq for possessing weapons of mass destruction to prove that with political globalization of the international system, sovereignty no longer provides absolute protection (Haass, 2006:2). Some scholars have foreseen the possibility of the creation of a world government which will regulate the interaction among governments and assure the rights arising from social and economic globalization. Because of its strong and wealthy economy, the United States has enjoyed a position of power among the world powers and is seen as the locus of such world government.

On its part, sovereignty, according to Bodin (Rodee, et al, 1983:35) "refers to the source of state's authority, regardless of its form of government". Traditionally, sovereignty is derived from a French word meaning 'above' or one who is superior to others. This means in effect that the sovereign is supreme. Bodin gives three fundamental attributes of sovereignty to include absoluteness, perpetuity and indivisibility. To Bodin, for the authority of the sovereign (king) to be complete, it must not be limited by traditions, past experience or shared with other institutions (Rodee, et al, 1983:35).

Sovereignty is therefore the exercise of absolute, perpetual and indivisible power, authority and control over a territory. A sovereign nation therefore can neither suffer derogation from any other authority outside its territory nor be dictated to by another country. A fundamental principle of the sovereignty of any state is the ability of such state to control what comes in and what goes out through its borders.

On the other hand, a state is a political configuration made up of people with its own government and totally free from outside control. It is therefore distinguishable from a nation, society or government by the possession of the principal characteristic called sovereignty, which is the authority to formulate, amend and execute law (Rodee, et al, 1983:35).

Objective of the Study:

This study seeks to investigate the impact of globalization on state sovereignty. It attempts to discover whether globalization will strengthen or undermine state sovereignty and on the basis of the discovery the writer attempts to proffer possible safeguards which states, especially the weak and poor countries of the south should put in place to protect their economies from the evil effects of globalization.

Globalization and State Sovereignty:

Many writers on the subject agree that globalization has the potential of undermining the political monopoly exercised by states over their territories. This is because it challenges "one of sovereignty's fundamental principles: the ability to control what crosses borders in either direction" (Haass, 2006:1). As an activity that transcends national boundaries, globalization deals a serious blow to state sovereignty. With globalization, the juridical claim by governments over their territory becomes increasingly very difficult.

Reich (1990) and Cable (1995) agree that the world is going to witness "the demise of the nation-state as a major power actor, the dissolution of 'national capitalisms' with their characteristic institutional arrangements, welfare systems and industrial policies, and ultimately worldwide convergence on one kind of economic system: Anglo-American-style free market capitalism" (Weiss, 1997:1).

Friedman as cited in Wikipedia argues that "globalized trade, outsourcing, supply-chaining, and political forces have changed the world permanently, for both better and worse". Some scholars speculate that the nation state is going to disappear in the near future. Fotopoulos also cited in Wikipedia defines political globalization as "the emergence of a transnational elite and the phasing out of the all powerful nation-state of

the statist period". Giddens believes that the nature of the nation state is changing dramatically due to globalization. "It is reducing the sovereignty of the nation with respect to global events which we need collaboration and trans-national institutions to deal with" (Word Press, 2007).

Quoting Wriston (1992), Featherstone, Lash and Robertson (1995) and Waters (1996), Waisbord & Morris believes that globalization renders "obsolete the basis of stateness, the existence and protection of a sovereign territory" (Waisbord & Morris). The author of "globalization" in *Wikipedia Free Encyclopedia* quotes Tom G. Palmer's definition of the term as "the diminution or elimination of state-enforced restrictions on exchanges across borders and the increasingly integrated and complex global system of production and exchange that has emerged as a result." (*Wikipedia*).

Globalization therefore re-enacts the imperialistic inclination of the European Industrial Revolution where European countries invaded Third World countries and forcefully integrated their economies into Western capitalist economy as appendages. The accusation of imperialism, specifically cultural imperialism is particularly leveled against international communication, especially the impact of foreign media on the lives and loyalties of citizens of any particular country. Unfortunately, the development of digital communication technology and systems that transcend geographical limitations, coupled with the unfettered worldwide expansion of media telecommunications companies represent the latest assault on state sovereignty. This informed the ban of satellite dishes dubbed "satanic dishes" by the Iranian government for bringing in offensive pictures into the country. Globalization of communication therefore undermines the attempts of authoritarian states to control information flow into their territories and consequently their political sovereignty (Waisbord & Morris). In other words, with globalization, the traditional concept of sovereignty, that states have exclusive power to make decisions within their territories without interference from other states or organizations, is moribund.

Globalization signals a "changing global context in which sovereignty is migrating from states ... to a loosely assembled global system" (Agnew, 2009).

Participants in the globalization debate therefore agree that “state power over territory is withering, giving rise to a different kind of state - one which has lost sovereignty, scaled back welfare programmes and industrial policy, and entered into multilateral governance arrangements. The primary locus for policymaking and for governing economic affairs is therefore shifting away from the nation-state, giving rise to a politics of less rather than more democracy” (Weiss, 1997:1).

Advantages of Globalization:

There are many advantages which nations stand to gain through globalization. Nations benefit, in aggregate terms, from trade and financial openness, although openness forces them into competition with one another. It is also believed that “the competitive pressures set off by economic openness will lead nations to pursue a similar, bare bones set of economic and social policies” (Mosley, 2005:2).

It is also believed that globalization leads to a convergence of national policies due to the financial openness it brings about. Research has shown that specialization is possible within globalization. Such studies specify that varying complexes of institutions can generate similar levels of overall economic performance, and these sets of business practices, training systems and worker organization provide comparative advantages to particular countries and sectors (Mosley, 2005:2).

In the area of Industry, globalization has led to the “emergence of worldwide production markets and broader access to a range of foreign products for consumers and companies, particularly movement of material and goods between and within national boundaries”. It has also led to a 100% increase in worldwide trade in manufactured goods from about \$95 billion to \$12 trillion since 1955. For instance, China's trade with Africa is reported to have risen sevenfold during 2000–2007 alone (*Wikipedia*).

Through globalization, global financial markets have emerged and borrower nations now have a better access to external financing. Due to expanded levels of trade and investment, more than \$1.5 trillion in national currencies were traded daily by the early part of the 21st century. Economically, there has been a “realization of a global common market, based on the freedom of exchange of goods and capital.” (*Wikipedia*).

Due to globalization, the economic fate of workers is no more tied to the fate of the economies of their countries. "With the advent of the information age and improvements in communication, ... workers compete in a global market, wages are less dependent on the success or failure of individual economies. This has had a major effect on wages and income distribution" (*Wikipedia*).

Globalism has also led to an increase in information flows between geographically remote locations. Arguably this is a technological change with the advent of fibre optic communications, satellites, and increased availability of telephone and internet (*Wikipedia*).

Limitation of Globalization:

The state and national governments will still occupy an important position in international politics for sometime to come because "domestic institutions play an important role in mediating pressures from the global economy and these institutions often are resilient in the face of global economic pressures" (Mosley, 2005:3).

Jessop (Jessop, 2003:15) agrees with Poulantzas that the national state is irreplaceable but its structure and functions would definitely be massively transformed in the face of globalization.

Ecologically, globalization brought about an advent of global environmental challenges such as "climate change, cross-boundary water and air pollution, over-fishing of the ocean, and the spread of invasive species" (*Wikipedia*). Hoekstra and Chapagain (2008) have identified the ecological danger developing countries stand to face from globalization. According to them, "since many factories are built in developing countries with less environmental regulation, globalism and free trade may increase pollution and impact on precious fresh water resources and without regulation, the standard of living in Third World countries would degenerate" (*Wikipedia*).

The competition set off by financial openness through globalization reduces governments' abilities to provide goods and services to their citizens and renders governments more accountable to external economic agents than to citizens (Mosley, 2005:1). Against this backdrop, some scholars believe that globalization actually decreased inter-cultural

contacts while increasing the possibility of international and intra-national conflict (*Wikipedia*).

Due to the negative ecological impact of globalization, rural dwellers in Third World countries who depend principally on natural resources for their sustenance suffers the blunt of ecological devastation of the environment. Globalization therefore aggravates poverty in rural areas while increasing the number of the wealthy, especially among the middle class in urban areas. This has exacerbated rural-urban drift in developing countries. Quoting a 2007 article in *The Economist*, *Wikipedia* blamed "increasing unrest in rural China on the growing gap in wealth between rural and urban areas ... plus growing worker discontent in industrialized areas" (*Wikipedia*).

The Future of the State in a Globalized World:

The past centuries have witnessed the conflict between the socialists and the capitalists, each side presuming to offer the best solution to the problems of the state. The traditional left presented a state-run socialist economy as the answer to the problems of nations while the traditional right believed that a market economy was the answer to the problems of the state. But unfolding events in the world has brought the realization that the welfare of citizens and the nation is better served sometimes by market-based enterprises and sometimes better by the state. Globalization has proved that the reform of the state and the review of the concept of sovereignty are crucial if any nation would make meaningful progress in the present world's political economy.

In an interview with Yamini Lohia of *Word Press* on the renewal of social democracy, Anthony Giddens, a sociologist and a member of the House of Lords and a former director of the London School of Economics believes that States must be prepared to innovate (*Word Press*, 2007).

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper has proved that from the emergence of the states system, states have been trying to preserve their sovereignty and national exclusiveness, but they have never really been able to do so in

absolute reality. The accusation that globalization is what has come to undermine territorial sovereignty of states is not wholly true.

Globalization has only come to prove that the traditional concept of sovereignty is not feasible in the light of modern international economic realities. It has merely further "complicated an already complex relationship between sovereignty and territory" (Agnew, 2009).

However, although the agents of globalization "undoubtedly influence contemporary national policy making, they have not brought about the demise of the nation-state. Nor have the pressures generated by such actors eliminated cross-national diversity in policy outcomes and political institutions. In the face of economic globalization, governments retain 'room to move', particularly in the developed world but also in developing nations" (Mosley, 2005:4). Moreover, domestic institutions play an important role in mediating pressures from the global economy, and these institutions often are resilient in the face of global economic pressures.

The economy of nations would crumble if entirely left to influence of external market forces. That is why some economic agents will favour government intervention – rather than market-oriented governance – in domestic economies (Mosley, 2005:2). Unfortunately, globalism is bringing about a world economic system where goods and services, investment, finance, and technology would flow across national borders without hindrance and their prices would be determined by forces outside the target market.

In reality therefore, continued progress in the integration of the world economy would render national governments less relevant. States would continue to lose their "powers not only to influence macroeconomic outcomes and to implement social programmes, but also to determine strategies for managing the industrial economy" (Weiss, 1997:1).

Recommendations:

From the conclusions arrived at in this paper, it is discovered that the nation-state would therefore become helpless in the face of a growing global economy. It is therefore pertinent that every nation of the Third World with weak economies should urgently harness their resources to

build strong economic base for their countries before opening up their economies to the international market economy if they are going to survive the global holocaust.

For this to be possible, the weak nations need first and foremost selfless leadership that is committed to the development of their countries. And such development would not be possible without the leadership first breaking the economic ties with which their former colonial powers subtly tied the economies of their former colonies to the Western capitalist economy.

Nigeria and other weak economic countries of the South can only achieve self-reliance through autochthonous development. Continued over reliance on the West would result in continued underdevelopment and a consequent inability to compete favourably within the world capitalist economy.

Local industries must be encouraged to grow through subsidies from the government, tax relief, government patronage of their products and selective imports to ensure that superior brand of the goods produced by such local industry are not imported as this will reduce the demand for those manufactured locally and thereby affect the particular industry adversely. The government must pay particular attention to export oriented industries in this regard.

In the same vein, the Nigerian government must systematically control the type of foreign investment they allow into the country to ensure only investments that would be beneficial to the country are allowed in.

Finally, the policy of indigenization and equity shareholding must be modified to make it mandatory for foreign conglomerates to source a higher percentage of their raw material inputs and labour internally. The Asian Tigers adopted similar strategies and this led them to successfully build up their economies (Owugah, 2003:250-252).

It is the belief of this paper that if these are done, it would strengthen Nigeria's economy and the economies of the developing countries and place them in a position to compete favourably with and benefit equally with other developed countries in the emerging world economy.

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